

Analyzing Persuasive Techniques in TED Talks

Brendan Boyle, Thelma Lax, Gregory Pflaumer, and Natchanun Sanitdee

Department of Languages, University of Helsinki

10.5.2024

Abstract

This report discusses a project involving a persuasive technique annotation scheme applied to a TEDTalk dataset. As TEDTalks are by convention persuasive texts with easily available transcripts, they are apt for a speculative exploration into the design and implementation of a corpus using TED as a dataset and its annotation for persuasive techniques. The 10 most watched TEDTalk videos are selected for the annotation tasks. The annotation is completed in the INCEpTION environment using 12 categories (tags) and 4 annotators. The datasets are categorized based on the persuasive technique framework (ethos, logos, pathos) (Higgins & Walker, 2012). Fleiss's k agreement coefficient (Fleiss, 1971) is used to measure the inter-annotator agreement (IAA). The score for each category is also reported. The overall score of 0.271 indicates a fair agreement level among annotators with the highest agreement on Call-To-Action (CTA) category at 0.653 and the lowest agreement on Pathos-Emotion (PAT-EMO) and Pathos-Rhetorical Question (PAT-RH) at 0.066 and 0.058, respectively. The categorical scores implies that anecdote-related categories (PAT-ANE, ETH-ANE, and LOG-ANE) are relatively challenging to annotate, and emotion-related categories (especially PAT-EMO and PAT-RH) are the most difficult ones.

Keywords: TEDTalks, Persuasive Techniques, Corpus Linguistics, Annotation.

1. Introduction

With an unprecedented amount of language data being produced and collected at a rate never seen before in history, online media platforms serve as a lucrative field for scholars to study linguistic phenomena. TEDTalk is a non-profit aiming to spread ideas through a short presentation by different speakers. With top videos having millions of views each, TEDTalk gains its popularity due to its powerful content. TEDTalk presentations, given a limited time of usually under 18 minutes, are packed with different linguistic tools to

draw attention from the audience and convince them. Therefore, TEDTalk discourse makes an interesting dataset to study persuasive techniques.

To investigate persuasive techniques in TEDTalks in a quantitative, scalable manner, this project has devised a novel annotation scheme for the express purpose of processing TEDTalk transcripts. The scheme is based on classical rhetorical persuasion theory, but adjusted for the multitude of persuasive techniques found in the TEDTalk genre. Annotation was conducted in the INCEpTION environment using 12 categories that were identified as necessary in order capture the depth of persuasive techniques across TEDTalks.

2. Background Theory and Framework

2.1 TED

TED Conferences, LLC is an American-Canadian non-profit founded in 1984. TED stands for Technology, Entertainment, and Design, the topics which the content initially covered Ludewige (2017). Later, its emphasis expanded to other fields, and in 2006, TEDTalks were made available online to the public.

2.2 Persuasive Techniques

Aristotle’s conception of rhetoric provides the foundation of the three main persuasive techniques (ethos, logos, pathos) in this project. The categorization is mainly inspired by the Elements of Rhetorical Appeals (Higgins & Walker, 2012) as demonstrated in Table 1.

In addition, from the initial observation of the transcriptions, an additional persuasive technique, Call-To-Action, is identified.

3. Data and Methods

3.1 Datasets

The sample dataset used for the initial construction of the corpus was compiled from the video transcripts of the ten most watch TED and TEDx Talks at the time of collection (March 2024) from <https://www.ted.com/talks>. The decision to use TED presentation data was inspired by the article from Ludewige (2017). Focusing on the most popular talks narrows down the set of thousands of TED Talks to a handful of speeches that carry the essence of the genre and are considered some of the more successful uses of rhetoric. The use of the corpus for a more in-depth study would require the addition of more transcripts. Given the scope and timeframe for this pilot investigation however, the quantity of data was limited to keep the annotation workload manageable. In addition

Appeal	Examples of persuasive techniques
ETHOS: credibility	Similitude Ingratiation Deference Expertise Self-criticism Inclination to succeed Consistency
PATHOS: emotion	Metaphors Identification, especially through cultural references such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sport • Under-privilege • Health, well-being • Hope, aspiration • Loyalty • Friendship • Sympathy
LOGOS: reason	Argumentation Logic Warrants/justifications Claims Data Evidence/examples (e.g. historica

Table 1: Elements of rhetorical appeals (Higgins & Walker, 2012)

to the files annotated by the team for analysis, a second set of transcripts were used as practice data for assembling and refining the codebook.

The official transcripts of TED presentations are available freely on the ted.com website. These are all manually created by human transcriptionists, not automatically generated. The transcript texts were collected by the corpus team from the website and compiled in .txt files. To remove metadata such as timestamps and audio descriptions, all files were cleaned simultaneously using OpenRefine (‘OpenRefine’, 2010–2024), a free, open-source data wrangling application. The clustering function was used to merge all instances of timestamps, and then a series of regular expression commands were performed to replace instances of timestamps and audio descriptions (e.g., *laughter*, *applause*, *cheering*) with a single space. Once the data was cleaned, all transcripts were uploaded onto INCEPTION simultaneously, but as separate files. To investigate persuasive techniques in TEDTalks in a quantitative, scalable manner, this project has devised a novel annotation scheme for the express purpose of processing TEDTalk transcripts. The scheme is based on classical rhetorical persuasion theory, but adjusted for the multitude of persuasive techniques found in the TEDTalk genre.

3.2 Annotation Process

This first round of annotation also acted as a calibration stage where all annotators discussed any disagreements and built a common understanding upon how to annotate the transcripts.

Annotation is done using the INCEpTION annotation environment. After logging in to the webpage, navigate to the project you wish to work on. Then select the **Annotation** tab from the right-hand toolbar. This will open a list of documents. Click on the assigned document.

3.3 Mitigating Biases

Selection biases: TEDTalks videos are selected from the top10 mostly watched videos. The transcriptions are assigned equally to each annotator based on a number of words.

Label biases: To minimize label biases, after the annotation guideline is created, annotators practice annotating in practice transcriptions and note the confusing labels before discussing and polishing the guideline.

3.4 Methods

Before starting, be sure that the *Persuasive Techniques* Layer is selected from the menu in the top left-hand corner. To create an annotation, double click on the target sentence. The entire sentence will automatically be highlighted. Select the desired tag from the left-hand side toolbar or use the provided hotkeys. The chosen tag will appear above the target sentence in the document. Make sure this tag is correct before moving on. If incorrect, the tag can be removed using the undo or delete buttons or hotkeys. If correct, double click on the next sentence to continue annotation. Upon the end of the document, check to make sure that every sentence has a tag. Once verified that the annotations are correct and complete, click on the lock button in the upper toolbar. This will lock the document and finish the annotation.

The application methods of the annotation scheme on the transcriptions are described in the succeeding steps below.

1. Select desired project. (Figure1)
2. Select Annotation from right-hand toolbar. (Figure2)
3. Select an assigned document. (Figure3)
4. Select Persuasive Techniques layer from top left corner menu. (Figure4)
5. Double click on sentence to create annotation. (Figure5)
6. Select appropriate tag from left-hand toolbar or using hotkeys. (Figure6)

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

7. Confirm tag is correct.
8. Double click on next sentence to continue annotating.
9. Verify that every sentence has been tagged.

Figure 5

Figure 6

10. Click on lock icon in upper toolbar to complete the document. (Figure 7)

Figure 7

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Annotation Reliability Analysis

4.1.1 Inter-Annotator Agreement (IAA)

Inter-annotator agreement is measured based on the transcription of the TEDTalk "Your body language may shape who you are" by Dr. Amy Cuddy (2012) annotated by 4 annotators. The transcriptions consist of 274 sentences. Because the task involves categorical annotations by 4 annotators, Fleiss's k agreement coefficient (Fleiss, 1971) is used to assess the annotation reliability. The annotations completed on the INCEpTION tool are populated into a .csv file in a tabular format. Tags (categories) are converted into numbers (1-12). The annotations for the first 10 sentences are shown in the Table 2.

Sentence	Annotator1	Annotator2	Annotator3	Annotator4
1	11	11	2	10
2	11	11	11	10
3	3	12	3	5
4	12	12	2	10
5	12	12	2	10
6	12	12	2	10
7	2	12	2	1
8	11	11	11	10
9	1	4	2	10
10	1	2	2	10

Table 2: Annotations of the first 10 sentences

Fleiss' kappa score is calculated by dividing the subtraction of the observed agreement P_o with the expected agreement P_e by the subtraction of 1 with the expected agreement P_e as demonstrated in the formula below. Table 3 from Landis & Koch (1977) shows a guide for interpreting the Kappa coefficient.

$$\kappa = \frac{\bar{P}_o - \bar{P}_e}{1 - \bar{P}_e}$$

Kappa	Agreement Strength
> 0.8	Almost Perfect
> 0.6	Substantial
> 0.4	Moderate
> 0.2	Fair
0 - 0.2	Slight
< 0	Poor

Table 3: Interpretation of Kappa coefficient

Using *kappam.fleiss* function in the *irr* library in *R*, the agreement scores between 4 annotators for each of the 12 categories, are shown in the Table 4.

- Subjects = 274
- Raters = 4
- Kappa = 0.271

Category	Tagset*	Kappa
1	PAT-ANE	0.261
2	PAT-EMO	0.066
3	PAT-RH	0.058
4	LOG-LOG	0.32
5	LOG-RH	0.545
6	LOG-STA	0.366
7	ETH-ANE	0.201
8	ETH-ETH	0.302
9	ETH-RH	0.132
10	LOG-ANE	0.171
11	CTA	0.653
12	NONE	0.124

Table 4: Fleiss’ Kappa score of 12 categories

*The description of each tagset can be found in the 6.1.3 Subtask and Tags.

According to the score table, the overall kappa score of 0.271 indicates a fair inter-annotator agreement. The kappa scores of each category reveal the highest agreement in category 11 Call-To-Action (CTA) at 0.653 followed by Logos-Rhetorical Question (LOG-RH) at 0.545. Logos-Statistics (LOG-STA), Logos-Logos (LOG-LOG), and Ethos-Ethos (ETH-ETH) receive a similar agreement level at 0.366, 0.32, and 0.302, respectively. Pathos-Anecdote (PAT-ANE), Ethos-Anecdote (ETH-ANE), and Logos-Anecdote (LOG-ANE) occupy somewhere in the middle range at 0.261, 0.201, and 0.171, respectively. Ethos-Rhetorical Question (ETH-RH) and None-Persuasive (NONE) see a relatively low agreement (0.132 and 0.124, consecutively). The least agreed on categories include Pathos-Emotion (PAT-EMO) and Pathos-Rhetorical Question (PAT-RH) at only 0.066 and 0.058, respectively.

An interesting observation can be made for the Call-To-Action category (CTA), which receives the highest agreement score. This implies that this category is easiest to be identified, and there was the least confusion among annotators. In addition, the scores of anecdote-related categories (PAT-ANE, ETH-ANE, and LOG-ANE) signal that annotators find it challenging to categorize anecdotes. Last but not least, emotion-related categories, especially PAT-EMO and PAT-RH, seem to be the trickiest task to handle. This urges for a more thorough revision of the codebook and a better understanding alignment process before real annotation.

5. Conclusion

This report has discussed the design and implementation a novel annotation schema for annotating persuasive techniques in TEDTalk presentations. The annotation schema is speculative as required of its purpose. The requirements toward success in annotator agreement were thus lax, and focus was placed on a thoughtful, cooperative learning process instead of producing a readily applicable scheme. This process proved fruitful, and though a modest reliability score was eventually achieved, improvements to the scheme and overall reliability success can be made using a sufficient annotator practice, testing, and repeated codebook revisions. In addition, a more comprehensive calculation of the agreement among subgroups of annotators should be made to get a more nuanced reliability assessment (Artstein, 2017). This project, despite its need for further development, may therefore provide any intrepid corpus design projects with an insight into design strategies and the challenges a corpus annotation project may face.

6. Appendix

6.1 Codebook

6.1.1 General Rules for Annotators

- The focus of the annotation task is on a sentence level.
- If a sentence contains more than one persuasive technique, the sentence needs to be annotated with only one technique that comes first in the annotation scheme table. For example, the following sentence “*Businesses can invest in better health care, better education and a higher minimum wage **so that** they create a group of people who are **hopeful** about the future and **less vulnerable** to the calls by extremists to burn the system down.*” contains PAT-EMO and LOG-LOG. LOG-LOG comes before PAT-EMO in the scheme table; therefore, it will be annotated as LOG-LOG.

6.1.2 Annotation Scheme

6.1.3 Subtask and Tags: Definition and Search Key Elements

The three main categories of persuasive technique are Ethos, Logos, and Pathos. Ethos and Pathos are divided into three sub-categories, and four sub-categories for Logos. When combined with Call-to-action and Non-persuasive categories, this makes a total of 12 tags. The descriptions below consist of explanation for each tag, the key elements, and example sentences to guide the annotation task.

Ethos

Ethos focuses on building audience trust. This is typically done by establishing credibility of the speaker and their argument. Does this sentence make the speaker appear credible, knowledgeable, or experienced?

After determining that a sentence uses Ethos, the next step is to determine the proper tag.

ETH-ETH - These statements aim to establish the credibility and authority of the speaker or source. They emphasize qualifications, expertise, experience, and trustworthiness, thus appealing to the audience's trust in the speaker's character or the reliability of the source.

Key elements: I, Expert, Credentials, Qualified, Experience, Trustworthy, Ph.D., Published author, Awards, Certified, Research-backed, Industry-leading, Renowned, Recognized

Credentials

- I've been studying civil wars for over 30 years.

ETH-ANE - Anecdotes are brief, personal stories or examples used to illustrate a point or convey a message. They make abstract concepts more relatable and vivid by providing concrete instances or narratives that the audience can easily understand and connect with emotionally.

Key elements: Let me tell you a story about, I remember when, One time, For instance, Picture this, Imagine if, Close your eyes and imagine, Put yourself in this situation

Personal experience and story

- *So here I was, sitting in a hotel conference room in suburban Virginia four times a year with a room full of really smart people.*

Years

- *Since 1946, over 250 civil wars have broken out and that number continues to increase.*

- *The US's democracy has been downgraded three times since 2016. It was downgraded because international election monitors had considered the 2016 election free, but not entirely fair.*

- *Between December of 2020 and early 2021, the United States was officially classified as an anocracy.*

ETH-RH - Rhetorical questions are used to engage the audience by prompting them to consider a particular point or line of thought. While not requiring a direct response, rhetorical questions stimulate reflection, curiosity, or agreement by implying an obvious or implied answer that aligns with the speaker's argument.

Key elements: Why not?, Isn't it?, What if?, Who wouldn't?, Have you ever wondered?, Can you imagine?, Don't you think?, Isn't that incredible?

Logos

Logos is the use of logic, rational argumentation, and objective evidence to convince the audience. Does this sentence explain the speaker's argument? Does it use examples from data or research (not from the speaker's own life experience)?

After determining that a sentence uses Logos, the next step is to determine the proper tag.

LOG-LOG - Logical arguments rely on reasoning, evidence, and rationality to persuade the audience. They present facts, data, research findings, and logical connections between premises and conclusions. Logical arguments aim to convince the audience through sound reasoning rather than emotional manipulation.

Key elements: Evidence, Studies show, Data, Facts, Research, Logical, Reasonable, Therefore, Consequently, Because, If... then, Due to, Premise, Conclusion, Supporting evidence, Counterargument

If-clause (cause and effect)

- *If a country had these two features, the task force considered it at high risk of political violence and put it on a watchlist.*

Cause and effect words

- That's **because** the CIA is legally not allowed to monitor the United States or its citizens.

LOG-ST A - Statistics and data provide empirical evidence and numerical support for arguments or claims. They enhance the persuasiveness of an argument by lending it credibility and demonstrating its factual basis. Statistics and data are particularly effective in appealing to the audience's logical reasoning and analytical thinking.

Key elements: According to, Studies have shown, Research indicates, Data suggests, Percent, Number, Majority, Significant, Highest, Lowest, Increase, Decrease, Comparison, Average, Trend, Pattern

Statistics

- There are now almost **50 percent** more civil wars than there were in 2001. - Since 1946, **over 250 civil wars** have broken out and that number continues to increase.

Numbers of categories

- It turns out that only **two factors** were highly predictive and they weren't the ones the experts expected.
- The task force was composed of **two types of people**, experts on civil war like myself and data analysts.

Tendency

- So powerful people **tend** to be, not surprisingly, more assertive and more confident, more optimistic.

Third (significant) person

- It's what **Marianne LaFrance** calls "standing in social quicksand."

LOG-ANE - This tag is for when the speaker uses a specific story or example to support their reasoning.

LOG-RH - This tag is for when the speaker uses a rhetorical question regarding their reasoning or argumentation.

- So why is this happening now?
- So how do you do this?

Pathos

Pathos refers to the speaker's attempts to evoke and influence the audience's emotions. The specific emotions depend on the topic and strategy, but may include anger, joy, pity, shock, empathy, and disgust. Pathos may be an effective part of a presentation, but is sometimes also used if a speaker does not have a solid logical argument.

PAT-EMO - Emotional appeals evoke feelings and sentiments in the audience, aiming to elicit an emotional response such as empathy, sympathy, joy, hope, or sadness. They often use poignant language and themes related to human experiences, struggles, or aspirations.

Key elements: Heartfelt, Inspiring, Moving, Touching, Heartwarming, Suffering, Struggle, Hope, Love, Happiness, Journey, Battle, Light at the end of the tunnel, Rising from the ashes

Emotional words

- *It's too **frightening** and it doesn't seem real.*

PAT-ANE - This tag is for when the speaker uses a specific story or example to evoke emotion.

PAT-RH - This tag is for when the speaker uses a rhetorical question to evoke emotion.

Call to Action

Other-CTA - Calls to action urge the audience to take a specific course of action, such as joining a cause, supporting a campaign, or making a purchase. They are designed to motivate immediate response or commitment from the audience by emphasizing the benefits or consequences of taking action and by invoking a sense of urgency or collective responsibility.

Key elements: Join us, Sign up, Support, Donate, Take action, Act now, Don't wait, Make a difference, Change the world, Together, we can, Let's make a difference, Join the movement, Be part of the solution

- *Or we could **use it to come together to show the world how to manage this change** and in the process **create a truly multiethnic, multi-religious democracy.***

- ***The first thing we have to do is** address the two big risk factors of civil war.*

- *To address anocracy, **we have to improve the rule of law.***

6.1.4 Points for alignment

- The use of ANE serves different purposes. ETH-ANE involves the stories about the speaker (usually with “I” or “we”). LOG-ANE is the stories that are used to back up the claims or support the arguments without the involvement of the speaker. If the stories also evoke emotions, than it is PAT-ANE. Therefore, in one story, different sentences can be tagged differently.
- Rhetorical questions (RH) necessitates some depth of interpretations. They are not usually simple questions like What does that mean?, the questions that are used to lead to the next topic like What do we do next? The next big question is...?, or the questions that check for confirmation like Right? Do you agree?
- Non-persuasive (N) usually involves the statements that are explanations, clarifications, descriptions or repetitions. For example, after showing a picture of people’s postures reflecting power dynamics on the slide, the speaker continues to explain the picture “So you’re folding up, you’re making yourself small.” or after the telling a story about an experiment, the speaker concludes “So two minutes lead to these hormonal changes that configure your brain to basically be either assertive, confident and comfortable, or really stress-reactive, and feeling sort of shut down.” However, if the statements include further interpretations like “When you’re touching your neck, **you’re really protecting yourself.**”, this is considered LOG.

Special thanks: The codebook is designed with an inspiration from Zeinert et al. (2021).

6.2 Task Allocation

A total of 10 most watched TEDTalk videos are assigned to each annotators equally based on a number of words. The allocation is initially meant for a more fine-grained agreement calculation both for all annotators, as well as among sub-groups of annotators.

	Title	Annotator
1	Do schools kill creativity?	T, B
2	Your body language may shape who you are	T, N, G, B
3	Inside the mind of a master procrastinator	G, T
4	The power of vulnerability	G, N
5	How great leaders inspire action	G, N
6	How to speak so that people want to listen	G, N
7	My philosophy for a happy life	T, B
8	What makes a good life? Lessons from the longest study on happiness	B, N
9	The next outbreak? We’re not ready	T, B
10	Looks aren’t everything. Believe me, I’m a model.	T, B

Table 5: Task allocation (T=Thelma, B=Brendan, G=Greg, N=Natchanun)

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